

Assessing the Effect of 'Jeopardy Game' on Enhancing Motivation and Mathematics Performance of Grade 9 Students

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Abstract: This study investigates the effectiveness of the Jeopardy Game as a gamified instructional strategy in enhancing motivation and academic performance in mathematics among Grade 9 students at the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology. Utilizing a quasi-experimental one-group pretest-posttest design, the research investigates the impact of interactive learning on students' engagement and performance in mathematical concepts. A pre-test was administered to evaluate baseline levels of student motivation and academic performance, followed by the implementation of a structured Jeopardy Game activity. After the intervention, a post-test assessed changes in students' scores and motivational levels. The findings reveal significant improvement in students' mathematics performance, as evidenced by higher post-test scores compared to pre-test outcomes. Moreover, students demonstrated a notable increase in motivation toward learning mathematics. These findings highlight the potential of gamified learning approaches to create a more engaging and effective educational environment. The study recommends the broader integration of game-based instructional methods, such as jeopardy games, into the curriculum to address diverse learning needs and enhance student motivation and academic performance in mathematics.

Keywords: *Jeopardy game, motivation, mathematics performance, game-based learning.*

Introduction

Mathematics is a foundation discipline that supports critical components of life, such as progress in science and technology, as well as the analytical ability required for everyday choices. Despite this, most students consider mathematics as one of the difficult subjects. The reason usually given for this perception is the failure to comprehend the complexity of the issues at hand, which creates a lack of interest and involvement. Consequently, many students feel unmotivated, which further decreases their interest in learning mathematics and can hinder their academic progress (Bernardo et al., 2022). Filipino students face significant challenges in mathematics education. This is evident in the poor performance results in mathematics assessments, including the Programme for International Student Assessment and the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Survey. In the PISA 2022 results, only 24% of Filipino students achieved basic proficiency in mathematics, with an average score of 355, which remains significantly below the OECD average score of 472 and shows minimal improvement from the 2018 assessment. Additionally, the TIMSS findings in 2019 revealed that the Philippines performed worse than all other participating countries in mathematics and science assessment, posting a score of 297 (Magas, 2023). Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated the current education crisis. A significant decline in students' mathematics achievement due to disruptions caused by the pandemic highlights the negative impact of disrupted learning environments on student motivation and performance (Diliberti et al., 2023).

Teachers play a crucial role in creating an environment that supports students' learning and enhances student performance in mathematics. Appiah, J.B. et al. (2022) stated that teachers who actively promote student motivation and self-efficacy can lead to better academic outcomes, as motivated learners are more likely to engage with challenging material. Additionally, effective teaching strategies, including fostering a supportive classroom environment and using varied instructional methods, significantly improve students' mathematical understanding and engagement (Tambunan et al., 2021). Active learning can be fostered if teachers employ innovative and different approaches to mathematics instruction, departing from conventional methods (Taranto et al., 2021). This statement is supported by Qomario et al (2020), who stated that innovative teaching approaches can enhance students' motivation and academic achievements.

One of the most promising teaching approaches is gamified instruction. Gamification in education is a strategy to enhance student engagement and motivation by introducing game elements into non-game environments such as conventional classrooms (Laura-De La Cruz et al., 2023). Furthermore, immediate feedback mechanisms inherent in gamified settings allow students to learn from their mistakes in real time, promoting a growth mindset essential for mastering complex mathematical concepts. A study conducted by Karp and Bush (2019) indicated that students in gamified environments reported greater enjoyment and confidence in their mathematical abilities compared to those receiving traditional instruction.

Gamification has two primary types: digital and non-digital gamification. Digital gamification leverages technology to enhance engagement through features like points, badges, and leaderboards. A study by Hwang et al. (2020) demonstrated that using gamified elements in mobile learning applications significantly improved student motivation and learning outcomes in mathematics. Additionally, a study by Hamari et al (2021) found that gamification in educational platforms leads to increased user satisfaction and motivation, further supporting the effectiveness of digital gamification in learning environments. However, the reliance on technology can create barriers for some learners, such as accessibility issues and distractions. While gamification can enhance learning outcomes, it also highlights challenges related to technology dependence, which may hinder students who lack access to digital resources (Karamert, 2021).

On the other hand, non-digital gamification involves using game elements in educational contexts without digital devices, such as board games and card games. A study by Zainuddin et al. (2023) indicated that non-digital gamification can enhance motivation and engagement among students and is a valuable educational strategy in high school mathematics education. However, further studies on non-digital gamification in learning are needed to highlight its effectiveness in educational contexts, particularly in mathematics. According to a systematic review by Wei et al. (2021), more than 50% of reviewed articles focused on digital gamification, leaving insufficient information on non-digital approaches and their effectiveness across different educational levels.

Jeopardy, a popular television game show originating from the United States, has been adapted for educational purposes in various studies as a game-based learning. A study by Brown et al. (2022) underscores that incorporating games like Jeopardy in education offers multiple benefits. These games are not only simple to design and engaging for students, but they also provide immediate feedback, enabling students to effectively assess their understanding and identify areas that need further improvement. Additionally, a study by Pathiraja (2024) observed that Jeopardy has a positive impact on student attitudes and perceptions, especially when students find the learning environment enjoyable. However, much of this research relies primarily on student surveys and observational data, with few studies investigating the effects of Jeopardy on actual academic performance following its implementation. Moreover, there remains a gap in a study on incorporating the Jeopardy game format specifically within the context of the mathematics subject. While its benefits in general educational settings are well-documented, limited studies have explored how effectively Jeopardy can enhance mathematical understanding, engagement, motivation, and performance among students.

Thus, with these statements supported by cited studies, this research aims to assess the effectiveness of the Jeopardy Game in enhancing both motivation and academic performance among Grade 9 students in mathematics, particularly in geometry.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized both descriptive and quasi-experimental one-group pretest-posttest design. A descriptive research design was used to describe the characteristics of a population. It collects data that is used to answer a wide range of what, when, and how questions about a particular population or group (Hassan, 2024). The one-group pretest-posttest design is a type of quasi-experiment in which the outcome of interest is measured twice: once before and once after participants are exposed to an intervention or treatment (Choueiry, 2021). The descriptive method will be used to describe students' motivation before and after the gamified instruction intervention. A pretest-posttest design was used to assess the performance of Grade 9 students before and after the Jeopardy game intervention.

Participants of the Study

This study was conducted at the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology – Laboratory High School, Gabaldon Campus, located in North Poblacion (Bitulok), Gabaldon, Nueva Ecija, 3131. The participants of the study were the fifty-four (54) Grade 9-Gold students enrolled at the said campus during the academic year 2024–2025.

Using a total population sampling technique, the researchers included all members of this specific group, as the entire population shared the characteristics relevant to the study. Total population sampling, a form of purposive sampling, is appropriate when the target group is small and well defined (Lavrakas, 2008). The study focused on this specific group to determine the effectiveness of the Jeopardy Game in enhancing student motivation and performance in mathematics.

Research Instrument

The researchers employed a 50-item pre-test and post-test assessment to evaluate the performance level of Grade 9 students in Mathematics. The use of pre-test and post-test measures is grounded in Classical Test Theory (CTT), which

posits that a learner's observed score reflects their true ability plus measurement error; administering parallel tests before and after an intervention helps determine changes attributable to the instructional strategy (Classical Test Theory and Reliability, 2017). The post-test contained items matched in content and difficulty to the pre-test to ensure reliability and to accurately measure learning gains.

Additionally, a researcher-developed motivation questionnaire was used to determine students' motivation toward mathematics before and after the gamified instructional intervention. The use of self-report Likert-type scales (4 – Strongly Agree, 3 – Agree, 2 – Disagree, 1 – Strongly Disagree) is supported by Likert's (1932) attitude measurement theory, which asserts that ordinal response formats effectively capture individuals' attitudes, perceptions, and motivational states.

Validity of Research Instrument

The researchers sought guidance from their research adviser, an expert in the field, to validate the pre-test, post-test, and survey questionnaire instruments, ensuring their clarity, applicability, and accuracy. To further strengthen the validation process, feedback was also solicited from 10 panel members, including a statistician, an English critic, and other faculty members. The Lawshe method was employed to quantitatively assess the content validity of the motivation questionnaire. Each item was rated by the experts as "essential," "useful but not essential," or "not necessary," and the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) for each item was computed. Items meeting or exceeding the minimum CVR threshold of 0.62 (for 10 experts) were retained. The overall Content Validity Index (CVI) was then calculated to determine the proportion of items deemed valid across all experts, ensuring that the instrument was both reliable and suitable for research purposes.

Reliability of Research Instrument

After validating the research instrument, twenty (20) students from Gabaldon Vocational Agriculture High School, who were not included in the study sample, were provided with the instruments to assess the reliability of the test questions. Cronbach's Alpha yielded reliability coefficients of 0.89 for the pre-test and 0.91 for the post-test, indicating high reliability in both assessments. For the survey questionnaire, Cronbach's Alpha was 0.75 before gamification and 0.87 after, suggesting improved reliability following the intervention.

Experimental Procedure

The experiment was conducted from January and March 2025, aligning with the Third Quarter of the Academic Year 2024-2025. The purpose was to assess the effectiveness of Jeopardy Game instruction on student learning performance. Researchers first provided a clear explanation of this instructional approach to ensure students understood its objectives and mechanics. A pretest was administered to establish baseline knowledge levels, and a survey questionnaire was given to measure students' motivation toward learning and gamification. Subsequently, students were divided into five diverse groups based on ability, ensuring a balanced mix of skills within each team.

The gamified instruction was carried out once a week, with each session lasting 60 minutes, consistent with the school's standard class duration. Each meeting focused on one Third Quarter Mathematics topic, specifically: (1) Proves Theorems on The Different Kinds of Parallelogram, (2) Proves the Midline Theorem, (3) Proves Theorems on Trapezoids and Kites, (4) Solves Problems involving Parallelogram, Trapezoids and Kites, and (5) Proves the Conditions for Similarity of Triangles. These topics served as the basis for the Jeopardy game questions.

To control for teacher effects, the same mathematics teacher-researcher facilitated all sessions, ensuring consistency in delivery, pacing, and instructional support. Students engaged in interactive, gamified activities that earned them points displayed on a classroom leaderboard, fostering a competitive yet collaborative learning environment. The top three groups each week were acknowledged and rewarded to further enhance motivation. For the Jeopardy-style activity, each team was provided with an identical board featuring mathematics problems, which they solved using the classic Jeopardy format. Questions varied in difficulty, with easier questions awarding fewer points and more challenging ones awarding higher points. Instead of buzzers, a 15-minute time limit was imposed to encourage time management and collaboration within the teams. The group that completed each category within the time limit earned the highest points.

Upon completion of the instructional sessions, the post-test same as the pretest and was administered to assess the effectiveness of the gamified instruction. The pretest and post-test scores were then compared and analyzed to determine whether gamified instruction led to a statistically significant improvement in learning outcomes and student motivation. Ethical considerations, such as informed consent and confidentiality, were strictly adhered to throughout the study, ensuring responsible and ethical research practices.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered in this study were analyzed using several statistical tools appropriate to the research objectives. To determine the students' level of performance before and after the Jeopardy game instruction, the researcher utilized frequency and percentage distribution, accompanied by the K-12 Descriptive Level to classify scores. The descriptive categories used were as follows: 0-10 (Did Not Meet Expectations - Very Low), 11-20 (Fairly Satisfactory - Low), 21-30 (Satisfactory - Moderate), 31-40 (Very Satisfactory - High), and 41-50 (Outstanding - Very High).

To identify whether a significant difference existed between the pre-test and post-test scores, a paired t-test was employed. This statistical test is appropriate for comparing two related measurements within the same group, allowing the researcher to determine whether the mean scores after the intervention differ significantly from those before the intervention. Cohen's d was computed to measure the strength of the intervention's effect, following the standard interpretation scale: 0.20 indicating a small effect, 0.50 a medium effect, and 0.80 and above a large effect.

Additionally, students' motivation toward mathematics was analyzed using the weighted mean based on a four-point Likert scale, with the following interpretations: 3.25-4.00 (Strongly Agree), 2.50-3.24 (Agree), 1.75-2.49 (Disagree), and 1.00-1.74 (Strongly Disagree). All collected data were carefully tallied, organized, and presented in tabular form, and computations were carried out using Microsoft Excel, SPSS, and Jamovi.

Results

Level of Performance of the Students Before and After the Jeopardy Game

Table 1 presents the performance results of 54 students before and after the implementation of Jeopardy Game instruction. The table shows a noticeable improvement in students' mathematics performance following the intervention. Before the Jeopardy Game, 32 of 54 students (59%) scored in the Fairly Satisfactory (Low) category, while 20 students (37%) scored in the Satisfactory (Moderate) category. Notably, 2 students (4%) did not meet expectations, scoring within the Very Low range.

In the same table presented, the distribution of scores shifted positively after the Jeopardy Game instruction. The number of students in the Fairly Satisfactory (Low) category dropped from 32 (59%) to 10 (19%), while those in the Satisfactory (Moderate) category increased significantly from 20 (37%) to 35 (65%). Additionally, 9 students (16%) advanced to the Very Satisfactory (High) category, which previously had no representation. No students remained in the Did Not Meet Expectations (Very Low) category after the intervention.

Table 1.

Level of Performance of Students before and after the Jeopardy Game.

Score	Verbal Description	Frequency	Pretest	Frequency	Posttest
0 - 10	Did Not Meet Expectations (Very Low)	2	4%	0	0%
11 - 20	Fairly Satisfactory (Low)	32	59%	10	19%
21 - 30	Satisfactory (Moderate)	20	37%	35	65%
31 - 40	Very Satisfactory (High)	0	0%	9	16%
41 - 50	Outstanding (Very High)	0	0%	0	0%
TOTAL		54	100%	54	100%

t-test Results and Effect Size

Table 2 presents the results of the statistical analysis comparing students' performance before and after the Jeopardy Game intervention. This indicates a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores ($t(53) = -11.96$, $p < 0.01$). The mean difference of 6.13 indicates a significant increase in post-test scores, showing that students performed better after the intervention. The correlation value of 0.791 suggests a strong relationship between the pre-test and post-test scores, meaning students who had higher initial scores still improved, and those with lower scores also showed progress. A t-value of -11.957 with 53 degrees of freedom was obtained, which is a large negative number, indicating a significant improvement in test performance. The p-value (0.000) confirms that this improvement is

statistically significant. Additionally, Cohen's *d* value of 1.63 represents a large effect size, further supporting the effectiveness of the Jeopardy game in enhancing students' mathematics performance. This result led to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0), proving that there is a statistically significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores.

Table 2.

Significant Difference Between Pre-test and Post-test Scores.

	Mean	Correlation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Cohen's d	Effect Size
Pretest-Posttest	-6.13	.791	-11.957	53	.000	1.63	Large

Students' Motivation in Mathematics Before the Jeopardy Game

Table 3 presents the students' motivation in mathematics before the introduction of gamified instruction. The data reveal that the respondents generally agreed with statements related to their motivation in mathematics, resulting in a total weighted mean of 2.88, which corresponds to the verbal interpretation of "Agree." Among the individual statements, it was found that students strongly agreed that mathematics is useful in real life, with a computed weighted mean of 3.26, the highest rating in the table. This suggests that students recognize the practical applications of mathematics, which could positively influence their engagement in the subject. Likewise, students expressed excitement about learning mathematics, obtaining a weighted mean of 3.00. Similarly, they acknowledged using strategies to learn mathematics effectively, with a computed mean of 2.93. These findings suggest that while students have a positive outlook on learning mathematics, their motivation levels are still moderate.

However, the data also highlights areas for improvement. The lowest-rated statement, "I feel confident when solving mathematical problems," received a weighted mean of 2.50, indicating that although students see the value of mathematics, they may struggle with self-efficacy in solving problems. Additionally, statements regarding participation in mathematics class and motivation to study outside the classroom yielded weighted means of 2.78 and 2.87, respectively, reflecting only moderate engagement. This suggests that while students had a generally favorable attitude toward mathematics, their motivation was not highly developed.

Table 3.

Students' Motivation in Learning Mathematics Before the Jeopardy Game.

Motivation in Learning Mathematics	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I find mathematics interesting and enjoyable.	2.94	Agree
2. I feel excited to learn mathematics.	3.00	Agree
3. I feel confident when solving mathematical problems.	2.50	Agree
4. I use strategies that ensure I learn mathematics well.	2.93	Agree
5. I actively participate in mathematics class.	2.78	Agree
6. I am confident I will do well on mathematics assignments and projects.	2.78	Agree
7. I believe I can master the knowledge and skills in the mathematics course.	2.81	Agree
8. I believe mathematics is useful in real life.	3.26	Strongly Agree
9. I feel motivated to study mathematics even outside the classroom.	2.87	Agree
10. I prefer traditional teaching methods over interactive learning.	2.91	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	2.88	Agree

Students' Motivation in Learning Mathematics After the Jeopardy Game

Table 4 presents the students' motivation in mathematics after the implementation of gamified instruction. The data reveals a total weighted mean of 3.28, which falls under the verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." This indicates that students' motivation in learning mathematics significantly improved following the use of gamification strategies.

Among the individual statements, the highest-rated item was "I believe mathematics is useful in real life," with a weighted mean of 3.46 and a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." This suggests that students' appreciation for the

practical applications of mathematics increased after gamified instruction. Likewise, students found mathematics interesting and enjoyable (3.37) and felt excited to learn mathematics (3.33), both of which were also rated as "Strongly Agree." These results indicate that gamification positively influenced students' engagement and enjoyment in mathematics.

Furthermore, the statement "I actively participate in mathematics class" also obtained a weighted mean of 3.33, showing that gamified instruction encouraged greater student involvement in class activities. Similarly, students felt more confident in solving mathematical problems (3.20) and using learning strategies effectively (3.28). These findings suggest that gamification contributed to improved self-confidence and problem-solving skills among students.

Table 4.

Students' Motivation in Learning Mathematics After the Jeopardy Game.

Motivation in Mathematics	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I find mathematics interesting and enjoyable.	3.37	Strongly Agree
2. I feel excited to learn mathematics.	3.33	Strongly Agree
3. I feel confident when solving mathematical problems.	3.20	Agree
4. I use strategies that ensure I learn mathematics well.	3.28	Strongly Agree
5. I actively participate in mathematics class.	3.33	Strongly Agree
6. I am confident I will do well on mathematics assignments and projects.	3.17	Agree
7. I believe I can master the knowledge and skills in the mathematics course.	3.24	Agree
8. I believe mathematics is useful in real life.	3.46	Strongly Agree
9. I feel motivated to study mathematics even outside the classroom.	3.20	Agree
10. I prefer learning mathematics through gamified instruction rather than traditional methods.	3.24	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	3.28	Strongly Agree

Discussion

The results of the study strongly corroborate existing literature on gamified and game-based learning, particularly in mathematics education. Prior studies by Smiderle et al. (2020) and Zainuddin et al. (2020) consistently demonstrated that gamification enhances student engagement, motivation, and academic performance. These outcomes closely mirror the present study's findings, which showed notable improvements in both students' post-test scores and motivation levels after implementing the Jeopardy Game. This alignment reinforces the view that gamified instructional strategies can serve as effective pedagogical tools for improving learning outcomes.

Moreover, the observed gains are consistent with the findings of Khoshnoodifar et al. (2023), Rahman et al. (2018), and Perez-Aranda et al. (2023), who emphasized that interactive and learner-centered approaches promote emotional engagement, sustained attention, and academic success. The Jeopardy Game, as an interactive learning tool, provided students with immediate feedback, opportunities for collaboration, and an enjoyable learning environment, all of which are key factors associated with improved cognitive and affective learning outcomes. These elements likely contributed to students' increased willingness to participate and engage meaningfully with mathematical concepts.

Specifically, the effectiveness of the Jeopardy Game aligns with the conclusions of Alsawaier (2017), Bayrak, F. (2024), and Brown et al. (2022), who found that Jeopardy-based activities reduce test anxiety, enhance conceptual understanding, and increase classroom participation, particularly in mathematics. The structured yet flexible format of the game encouraged active recall, rapid problem-solving, and peer interaction, which are critical components of deep learning. Additionally, Bishara (2018) highlighted that active learning strategies are particularly beneficial for low-performing students—a finding strongly supported by this study, as evidenced by the noticeable reduction in the number of students classified as low performers following the intervention.

The significant improvement in students' post-test scores suggests that the Jeopardy Game effectively promoted active participation, quicker recall, and deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. The competitive yet collaborative nature of the activity appears to have heightened students' focus and motivation, enabling them to process information more efficiently and retain it more effectively. This combination of competition and collaboration likely fostered a positive learning atmosphere that encouraged students to take academic risks without fear of failure.

Furthermore, the increase in motivation scores reinforces the premise that gamified learning environments satisfy students' psychological needs for engagement, autonomy, and competence—key elements emphasized in motivational theories and supported by Hamari et al. (2016). Students who initially exhibited low confidence in problem-solving demonstrated improved self-efficacy after repeated exposure to interactive and rewarding learning activities. This outcome aligns with the findings of Smiderle et al. (2020) and Zainuddin et al. (2020), which suggest that gamification can positively influence students' attitudes toward learning by fostering enjoyment and a sense of achievement.

The findings of this study have important implications for mathematics instruction and the broader K–12 curriculum. The significant gains in academic performance indicate that gamified strategies such as the Jeopardy Game can be effectively integrated into regular classroom instruction to reinforce lessons, enhance retention, and promote active learning. Teachers may utilize gamified approaches not only as review tools but also as formative assessment strategies to reduce mathematics anxiety, increase participation, and accommodate diverse learning needs through differentiated instruction.

Despite these positive outcomes, several limitations must be acknowledged. The study involved only one section of Grade 9 students from a single school, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the intervention was conducted over a relatively short period, and long-term retention of learning was not examined. The study also focused exclusively on Jeopardy-type gamification; other game-based formats and digital platforms may yield different or complementary effects. Future research may address these limitations by employing longitudinal designs, comparing multiple gamified strategies, and involving larger and more diverse student populations to further validate and extend the findings.

Conclusion

The findings of this study lead to the conclusion that the Jeopardy Game is an effective instructional strategy for improving both students' mathematics performance and their motivation toward learning. Prior to the intervention, most learners performed at Fairly Satisfactory (Low) levels, but after the implementation of the gamified instruction, a significant number of students advanced to higher performance categories, including the Very Satisfactory (High) level. The statistically significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores confirms that the Jeopardy Game had a meaningful and positive impact on students' learning outcomes. Students also demonstrated increased motivation, showing greater enjoyment, active participation, confidence, and appreciation for mathematics.

These conclusions are important because they highlight the value of integrating gamified learning approaches into mathematics education, especially at the junior high school level, where student engagement often declines. The results support previous studies emphasizing the effectiveness of gamification in enhancing engagement, motivation, and academic achievement, thereby extending growing evidence that interactive and competitive learning environments can strengthen understanding and retention.

Practically, the findings suggest that educators may incorporate Jeopardy-style games as supplementary tools for reviewing lessons, reinforcing concepts, and promoting collaboration and healthy competition in the classroom. Theoretically, the study contributes to the body of knowledge advocating for student-centered instructional models that blend motivation with cognitive development. Moving forward, future research may explore the long-term effects of gamified instruction, examine its impact on diverse learning groups, or compare different game-based strategies to determine which formats yield the greatest academic and motivational benefits. These insights may also guide school policies and curriculum planning aimed at fostering more engaging, adaptive, and effective mathematics instruction.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, several recommendations are proposed to enhance the integration of gamified instruction in mathematics education. School administrators are encouraged to support and promote the use of gamified learning tools, such as the Jeopardy Game, by providing resources, training, and opportunities for teachers to apply innovative instructional strategies. Mathematics teachers are likewise encouraged to incorporate gamified approaches into their lessons to create more interactive, engaging, and motivating learning experiences for students. For learners, active participation in such activities is recommended, as gamified instruction can increase their interest in mathematics, strengthen their problem-solving confidence, and foster collaboration and teamwork. Finally, future researchers are advised to conduct further studies exploring the long-term impacts of gamified learning strategies, such as the Jeopardy Game, on retention, conceptual understanding, and overall academic performance, and to examine their effectiveness across different grade levels, subjects, and learning contexts.

Author Contributions

Both authors contributed equally to the completion of this research, with one author focusing on supervision, validation, and review of the study, while the other took the lead in data gathering, analysis, and manuscript writing.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no competing interests.

AI Use Declaration

An AI tool (ChatGPT, OpenAI version 5) was used for language editing. The authors reviewed and are fully responsible for the final content.

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